

Peroxyacid oxidations : kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones by peroxomonophosphoric acid and peroxomonosulfuric acid

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The kinetics of oxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones by peroxomonophosphoric acid and peroxomonosulfuric acid have been studied at different pH over the temperature range 308–328 K. The reactions are of second order; first order each in peroxy acid and in substrate concentrations at constant pH. From the pH-rate data the relative reactivities of different peroxy and substrate species have been determined. The results are interpreted in terms of nucleophilic attack by peroxy species on the neutral as well as protonated forms of the substrate molecule followed by oxygen-oxygen bond fission to give the products. Thermodynamic parameters for the reactions have been evaluated.

We have studied the oxidation of α - and β -diketones^{1,2}, and of α -keto acids³ by peroxomonophosphoric acid earlier. These reactions were shown to be initiated by nucleophilic attack of the peroxomonophosphoric acid species on the carbonyl-carbon of the substrate molecule. The oxidation of β -diketones² involved the intermediate formation of enol epoxide, whereas in case of α -diketones¹ it followed a Baeyer-Villiger type mechanism. The present paper deals with the peroxomonophosphoric acid (PMPA) and peroxomonosulfuric acid (PMSA) oxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones (hereafter referred to as 'ketone') where the carbonyl-carbon atom and the β -ethylenic carbon atom are activated for nucleophilic attack by the peroxy anions.

Results and discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of mesityl oxide (MO) and benzalacetone (BA) by peroxomonophosphoric acid and by peroxomonosulfuric acid, at constant pH and ionic strength (μ), follow second-order kinetics; first order in each [peroxy acid] and [ketone] (Tables 1 and 2). The rate law being

$$\text{Rate} = k_2' [\text{peroxy acid}]_t [\text{ketone}]_t$$

where k_2' is the observed second-order rate constant and t denotes total concentration.

The rate is not influenced by ionic strength. Radical trapping agents like acrylamide also do not have any influence on the oxidation rate (Table 1).

The kinetics of oxidation of mesityl oxide and benzalacetone by PMSA have been investigated in the pH ranges 0–10 and 0–11 respectively. The oxidation of mesityl oxide by PMPA has been studied in the pH range 0–6.7,

Table 1. Oxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones by peroxomonophosphoric acid^a

Substrate [S]	$10^3[S]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4[\text{PMPA}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3k_2'$ ^b dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Mesityl oxide ^c	9.95	6.2	5.9
	25.8	6.3	5.6
	50.1	6.5	5.25
	100	6.1	6.07
	50.3	5.3	3.27 ^d
	50.2	2.93	5.27
	50.2	10.6	5.06
	50.1	21.0	4.40
	50.6	5.95	5.66 ^e
	50.6	5.55	6.10 ^f
	50.6	6.56	5.43 ^g
50.5	6.1	5.4 ^h	
Benzalacetone ^d	24.1	4.92	8.5
	40.6	4.29	8.8
	78.4	5.63	8.3

^a[H⁺] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.3 mol dm⁻³, 308 K; ^bObserved second-order rate constant; ^cAqueous; ^dCH₃CN : water = 40 : 60% (v/v); ^e μ = 0.2 mol dm⁻³; ^f μ = 0.6 mol dm⁻³; ^g μ = 0.8 mol dm⁻³; ^h[Acrylamide] = 50.1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³.

and that of benzalacetone in the [H⁺] range (0.05–0.5) mol dm⁻³. The influence of pH on the oxidation rate is presented in Tables 3 and 4 and shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

The oxidation of benzalacetone, which has been studied in aqueous-acetonitrile medium (owing to solubility problems) could not be carried out at higher pH in case of PMPA because of slowness of the reaction and high oxidant decomposition.

Peroxy acids react with olefins to produce epoxides^{4,5}; the mechanism of this reaction involves nucleophilic attack

Table 2. Oxidation of α, β -unsaturated ketones by peroxomonophosphoric acid

Substrate [S]	$10^3[S]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4[PMSA]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3k_2^a$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Mesityl oxide ^b	10.2	2.99	8.31
	22.1	3.06	8.53
	41.1	3.30	8.47
	100	2.51	8.75
	40.9	1.55	8.84
	41.0	3.32	8.47
	40.9	3.99	9.06
	40.9	4.99	9.06
Benzalacetone ^c	12.1	5.48	2.04
	20.0	4.95	2.19
	41.7	4.65	2.19
	88.5	4.83	2.31

^aObserved second order rate constant, ^bAqueous, [H⁺] = 0.25 mol dm⁻³ μ = 0.3 mol dm⁻³ ^cCH₃CN-water = 40-60% (v/v) [H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³ μ = 0.6 mol dm⁻³

Table 3 (contd)

	5.95	-	-	1.74 (2.05)
	6.6	-	-	2.59 (2.40)
	6.65	0.50 (0.63)	-	-
	6.85	-	1.54 (1.40)	-
PMSA	0	17.3 (12.5)	18.5 (21.5)	36.5 (35.9)
	0.3	12.3 (10.1)	14.7 (16.5)	23.6 (29.9)
	0.6	9.11 (8.15)	13.3 (13.3)	21.8 (23.4)
	1	7.35 (6.58)	10.8 (10.8)	19.8 (18.9)
	2	5.61 (5.42)	10.4 (8.88)	14.5 (15.0)
	3.1	4.75 (5.28)	-	-
	3.65	-	-	10.5 (15.2)
	3.80	-	9.3 (8.7)	-
	5.10	-	10.4 (8.7)	-
	5.12	5.79 (5.29)	-	-
5.38	-	-	18.5 (15.3)	
5.75	6.93 (5.34)	-	-	
6.06	-	-	20.0 (15.6)	
6.59	12.5 (6.05)	16.2 (9.4)	30.9 (16.2)	
7.08	-	-	31.6 (19.2)	
8.49	-	64.9 (64.9)	108.9 (108.1)	
8.73	54.1 (57.2)	-	-	
9.30	125 (135)	-	-	
9.54	-	307 (306)	550 (506)	
10.07	242 (247)	401 (405)	600 (714)	

The values in parentheses represent $10^3k_2^a$ (calcd) dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹ ^aAqueous

Table 3. Oxidation of mesityl oxide by peroxyacids effect of pH^a

Peroxyacid	pH	$10^3k_2^a$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹		
		35°	45°	55°
PMPA	0.3	26 (28)	-	39.5 (42.0)
		11.9 (9.85)	16.6 (16.3)	24.4 (24.4)
	1.0	6.27 (10)	9.35 (9.89)	13.1 (15.3)
		4.1 (8.2)	5.65 (5.78)	7.55 (9.37)
	2.0	-	1.55 (1.53)	1.92 (2.57)
		0.794 (0.840)	-	-
	2.6	-	-	0.684 (0.945)
		3.2	-	0.212 (0.296)
	3.45	0.123 (0.135)	-	-
	3.55	-	-	0.481 (0.45)
	3.85	-	0.234 (0.255)	-
		4.0	0.098 (0.131)	-
	4.45	-	0.319 (0.332)	-
	5.0	-	-	0.93 (0.99)
	5.05	0.238 (0.282)	-	-
	5.75	-	0.695 (1.04)	-
	5.9	0.364 (0.54)	-	-

of the olefinic double bond on peroxo-oxygen. In the epoxidation of α, β -unsaturated ketones using alkaline hydrogen peroxide, the nucleophilic behaviour of H₂O₂ has been reported⁶. The carbonyl group confers electrophilic character on the ethylenic double bond which is then attacked by HOO⁻.

Table 4. Oxidation of benzalacetone by peroxyacids : effect of pH^a

Peroxyacid	pH	$10^3 k_2'$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹		
		35°	45°	55°
PMPA	0.3	2.97 (2.33)	5.41 (4.10)	8.9 (7.4)
	0.5	2.15 (1.92)	3.75 (3.40)	6.3 (6.13)
	0.7	1.23 (1.50)	2.61 (2.68)	4.5 (4.8)
	1.0	0.88 (0.95)	1.32 (1.7)	2.24 (3.1)
	1.3	0.50 (0.56)	0.9 (1.0)	1.65 (1.87)
	PMSA	0	3.94 (2.57)	—
0.3		2.20 (2.08)	—	—
0.6		1.13 (1.54)	—	—
1		0.550 (0.720)	—	—
2.28		0.183 (0.300)	—	—
3.96		0.270 (0.270)	—	—
4.87		0.480 (0.260)	—	—
6.46		0.898 (0.310)	—	—
7.12		1.65 (0.504)	—	—
8.44		6.22 (4.68)	—	—
8.88		9.99 (10.0)	—	—
9.78		28.8 (33.4)	—	—
11.03		46.8 (45.9)	—	—

The values in parentheses represents $10^3 k_2'(\text{calcd.})$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹.
^aCH₃CN : water = 40 : 60% (v/v), 308 K.

Further studies on the oxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones using *t*-butyl hydroperoxide⁷, peroxyacetic acid⁸⁻¹⁰, alkaline H₂O₂^{6,11}, have revealed that the peracid molecule may attack either on the carbonyl-carbon followed by rearrangement to give enol esters or on the β -carbon atom of the conjugate olefin to yield epoxide.

The acid catalysis in the reactions of carbonyl compounds is normally traced to the protonation of the carbonyl group¹².

The reaction¹⁰ of benzalacetone, an α,β -unsaturated ketone,

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_2'$ vs pH : (A) PMPA-mesityl oxide, (B) PMSA-mesityl oxide.

with peracetic acid has been reported to involve protonation of the $>C=O$ group.

In the present study, the acid catalysis in the pH region 0–3.5 could be explained by assuming the participation of both the neutral as well as protonated forms of the substrate molecule in the reaction.

In aqueous solution, PMPA exists¹³ as H₃PO₅, H₂PO₅⁻, HPO₅²⁻ and PO₅³⁻ depending on the pH (eqs. 3–5)

Since in the pH range 0–7, PMPA exists¹³ as H₃PO₅,

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k'_2$ vs pH : (A) PMPA-benzalacetone, (B) PMSA-benzalacetone.

$H_2PO_5^-$ and HPO_5^{2-} , the reaction in this range of pH involves the interaction of these anions with the substrate species. In the pH range 0–3.5, both S and SH^+ react with the PMPA species H_3PO_5 , $H_2PO_5^-$, whereas in pH range 3.5–7, the ketone which exists mainly in neutral form reacts with $H_2PO_5^-$ and HPO_5^{2-} .

The probable steps of oxidation are presented in eqs. 6–10.

The rate law pertaining to these reaction steps, in the case of mesityl oxide, is given by eq. 11.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{PMPA}]_t}{dt} \\ &= k_1[H_3PO_5][S] + k_2[H_3PO_5][SH^+] + k_3[H_2PO_5^-][S] \\ &\quad + k_4[H_2PO_5^-][SH^+] + k_5[HPO_5^{2-}][S] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) rearranges to give eq. (12)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{PMPA}]_t}{dt} \\ &= \left\{ \frac{k_2K_a[H^+]^3 + k_4K_1K_a[H^+]^2 + k_1[H^+]^2 + k_3K_1[H^+] + k_5K_1K_2}{(K_1K_2 + K_1[H^+] + [H^+]^2)(1 + K_a[H^+])} \right\} [\text{PMPA}]_t [S]_t \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where

$$[\text{PMPA}]_t = [H_3PO_5] + [H_2PO_5^-] + [HPO_5^{2-}] \quad (13)$$

$$\text{and } [S]_t = [S] + [SH^+] \quad (14)$$

Eq. (12) changes to eq. (15)

$$k'_2 = \frac{k_2K_a[H^+]^3 + k_4K_1K_a[H^+]^2 + k_1[H^+]^2 + k_3K_1[H^+] + k_5K_1K_2}{(K_1K_2 + K_1[H^+] + [H^+]^2)(1 + K_a[H^+])} \quad (15)$$

In the oxidation of benzalacetone, since the reaction involves interaction of the predominant oxidant species, H_3PO_5 and $H_2PO_5^-$ with S and SH^+ , the rate equation (15) reduces to eq. (16).

$$k'_2 = \frac{k_2K_a[H^+]^2 + k_4K_1K_a[H^+] + k_1[H^+] + k_3K_1}{(K_1 + [H^+])(1 + K_a[H^+])} \quad (16)$$

The value of K_a , as determined kinetically, is found to be 0.98 mol dm^{-3} for mesityl oxide and 3.3 mol dm^{-3} for

benzalacetone. The average values of resolved rate constants for the oxidation of mesityl oxide and benzalacetone have been determined by least-squares analysis in accordance with eq. (15) and eq. (16) respectively and are recorded in Table 5. The rate constants k'_2 (calcd.), computed from eq. (15) and eq. (16) for oxidation of the two ketones at different pH, are recorded in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 5. Summary of resolved rate data for oxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones by H_3PO_3 , $H_2PO_3^-$ and HPO_3^{2-} at different temperatures

Reaction	Rate $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	35°	45°	55°
Mesityl oxide^a				
$H_3PO_3 \sim S$	$10^4 k_1$	0.56	0.83	1.2
$H_3PO_3 \sim SH^+$	$10^2 k_2$	5.8	8.0	10.8
$H_2PO_3^- \sim S$	$10^4 k_3$	1.01	2.0	3.5
$H_2PO_3^- \sim SH^+$	$10^2 k_4$	8.0	14.6	24.3
$HPO_3^{2-} \sim S$	$10^4 k_5$	6.6	14.0	25.0
Benzalacetone^b				
$H_3PO_3 \sim S$	$10^6 k_1$	4.5	8.1	13.0
$H_3PO_3 \sim SH^+$	$10^3 k_2$	3.7	6.4	11.5
$H_2PO_3^- \sim S$	$10^6 k_3$	7.14	15.2	30.4
$H_2PO_3^- \sim SH^+$	$10^3 k_4$	4.0	7.62	14.0

^aAqueous; ^b CH_3CN : water = 40 : 60% (v/v).

In the structure of peroxomonosulfuric acid¹⁴ one proton is a sulfuric acid proton and the other is a hydrogen peroxide proton. The pK_a value of the sulfuric acid proton lies in the high acidity region while the hydrogen peroxide proton has a pK_a value¹⁴ of 9.4.

In aqueous solution PMSA exists as HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-}

For the oxidation of mesityl oxide and benzalacetone by PMSA, in the range of pH studied, the dependence on pH can be explained by a mechanism in which the protonated and neutral forms of the ketone molecule react simultaneously with HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} in parallel reactions.

The rate law pertaining to these reaction steps is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[PMSA]_t}{dt} \\ &= k_6[HSO_5^-][S] + k_7[HSO_5^-][SH^+] + k_8[SO_5^{2-}][S] \\ &\quad + k_9[SO_5^{2-}][SH^+] \quad (22) \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left\{ \frac{k_6[H^+] + k_7 K_a [H^+]^2 + k_8 K_4 + k_9 K_a K_4 [H^+]}{(K_4 + [H^+])(1 + K_a [H^+])} \right\} [PMSA]_t [S]_t \quad (23)$$

where $[PMSA]_t = [HSO_5^-] + [SO_5^{2-}]$ (24)

Eq. (23) rearranges to give eq. (25)

$$k'_2 = \left\{ \frac{k_6[H^+] + k_7 K_a [H^+]^2 + k_8 K_4 + k_9 K_a K_4 [H^+]}{(K_4 + [H^+])(1 + K_a [H^+])} \right\} \quad (25)$$

The average values of k_6 , k_7 , k_8 and k_9 obtained by least-squares analysis of the data according to eq. (25), are given in Table 6. These values have been used to calculate k'_2 (calcd.) in Tables 3 and 4

Table 6. Summary of resolved rate data for oxidation of α,β -unsaturated ketones by HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} at different temperatures

Reaction	Rate $dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$	35°	45°	55°
Mesityl oxide^a				
$HSO_5^- \sim S$	$10^3 k_6$	4.65	9.63	13.01
$HSO_5^- \sim SH^+$	$10^2 k_7$	1.99	4.10	5.72
$SO_5^{2-} \sim S$	$10^2 k_8$	29.9	62.0	86.3
$SO_5^{2-} \sim SH^+$	$10^{-6} k_9$	1.61	3.32	4.60
Benzalacetone^b				
$HSO_5^- \sim S$	$10^5 k_6$	1.20	-	-
$HSO_5^- \sim SH^+$	$10^3 k_7$	4.41	-	-
$SO_5^{2-} \sim S$	$10^2 k_8$	4.70	-	-
$SO_5^{2-} \sim SH^+$	$10^{-5} k_9$	1.40	-	-

^aAqueous ; ^b CH_3CN : water = 40 : 60% (v/v).

Average values of the net activation parameters for the reactions involving different peroxo and substrate species have been determined from the linear Arrhenius plots of log rate versus T^{-1} , and are recorded in Table 7.

The energy of activation for the oxidation of mesityl oxide and benzalacetone lie in the range 38–45 $kJ mol^{-1}$. Homolytic cleavage of the peroxide bond requires¹⁵ an energy of activation of $\approx 138 kJ mol^{-1}$. Further, the observations like (a) bimolecular second-order kinetics, (b) negative entropy of activation, (c) insensitivity of rate to radical trapping agents, show that these reactions involve

Table 7. Activation parameters for the oxidation of mesityl oxide and benzalacetone by different peroxy species

Reaction	Mesityl oxide ^a		Benzalacetone ^b	
	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
H ₃ PO ₅ ~S	29.5	-231	42.2	-211
H ₃ PO ₅ ~SH ⁺	24.0	-191	45.0	-145
H ₂ PO ₅ ~S	50.0	-160	58.5	-154
H ₂ PO ₅ ~SH ⁺	44.0	-122	50.0	-128
HPO ₅ ²⁻ ~S	54.0	-132	-	-
HSO ₅ ~S	42.01	-154	-	-
HSO ₅ ~SH ⁺	41.9	-142	-	-
SO ₅ ²⁻ ~S	41.9	-119	-	-
SO ₅ ²⁻ ~SH ⁺	41.5	8.22	-	-

^aAqueous; ^bCH₃CN : water = 40 : 60% (v/v).

polar mechanisms¹⁶.

From the magnitude of reactivities of different peroxy species (Table 5), it is seen that the reaction is facilitated by the more nucleophilic peroxy species. The protonated α,β -unsaturated ketone reacts at higher rate than the neutral form.

The pH-rate profiles observed in case of PMPA~MO, PMSA~MO and PMSA~BA reactions reveal that the rate of oxidation decreases with increasing pH in the lower range showing a rate-minimum which is then followed by increase of rate with pH in the higher range.

The enhancement of rate on either side of the rate-minimum observed might be due to an increase in the concentration of more electrophilic substrate species, SH⁺, or due to increase in the concentration of more nucleophilic peroxy species.

It is evident from the structure (1) that in the reactions of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds, the carbonyl-carbon and β -ethylenic carbon both are activated for nucleophilic attack¹⁷ by peroxy anions.

The nucleophilic attack of peroxy species on the carbonyl-carbon in the case of mesityl oxide is hindered because of electron accession to the reaction center due to the presence of methyl groups on the β -carbon⁶. The presence of a phenyl group at the β -carbon, in case of benzalacetone, however, favours nucleophilic attack on the carbonyl carbon^{9,10}, which may consequently result in the formation of an enol ester or lactone by way of Baeyer-Villiger mechanism; the migratory aptitude of the unsaturated group being several times higher

than the methyl group⁹. Winkert and Rubin¹⁰, in the oxidation of benzalacetone by alkaline hydrogen peroxide, have suggested the intermediate formation of benzyl carbonium ion, which is being stabilised by phenyl group.

Scheme 1 outlines the overall steps that may probably be taking place in the oxidation of mesityl oxide by peroxy species.

Scheme 1

The epoxy ketone (A) on further reaction^{18,19} with peroxy species, or on hydrolytic cleavage, might probably have led to the formation of (CH₃)₂CO, HCOOH and CH₃COOH (Scheme 2). The products HCOOH and CH₃COOH have been detected by spot tests^{20,22}.

Scheme 2

Experimental

PMPA solutions were prepared by acid hydrolysis of K₄P₂O₈. The potassium salt of Caro's acid, oxone (2KHSO₅·KHSO₄·K₂SO₄) (Dupont) was used to prepare PMSA so-

lutions. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Mesityl oxide was distilled just before use (b.p. 129–130°), and the constant boiling middle fraction was used in the experiments. Benzalacetone (Aldrich) was recrystallised from *n*-hexane. Acetonitrile was distilled over P₂O₅ (b.p. 80–82°). Sodium perchlorate prepared *in situ* by neutralizing perchloric acid with carbonate-free sodium hydroxide, was used for adjusting ionic strength of the medium. All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water, the second distillation being from KMnO₄. Acidity of the solution was maintained by adding calculated amounts of HClO₄ or standard buffers such as acetic acid-sodium acetate, sodium hydroxide-potassium hydrogen phthalate, KH₂PO₄-K₂HPO₄, Na₂CO₃-NaHCO₃. A Digisum Electronics DI-707 pH meter was used.

The kinetics was followed by measuring the rate of disappearance of peroxy acid, the estimation of which was made iodometrically using standard thiosulfate; PMPA estimation was done in an acetate buffer of pH 4–5 with a drop of ammonium molybdate solution²¹. The observed second-order rate constants (k_2') was calculated by dividing pseudo-first-order rate constant with respect to peroxy acid disappearance by the substrate concentration. The rate constants were reproducible to $\pm 5\%$. The self-decomposition of PMPA or PMSA was found to be either nil or negligibly small under our experimental conditions. The temperature was constant to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Product study : Potassium peroxodiphosphate (8.67×10^{-3} mol) was dissolved in water (25 ml) containing 0.3 mol dm^{-3} HClO₄. The system was left for 3.5 h at 35° to ensure complete hydrolysis. To this solution 3.98×10^{-3} mol of mesityl oxide was added. The mixture was then stirred and allowed to stand overnight at 35°.

Tests with ammoniacal AgNO₃, resulted in an opalescence of metallic silver indicating the presence of formic acid. Acetic acid in presence of formic acid was identified by colour reaction with a solution of sodium nitroprusside containing morpholine^{20,22}.

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